

CHARACTERISTICS OF MENTAL DEVELOPMENT OF CARE GIVERS

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Abstract. *In any country, in any society, there were, are and will be children without parental care. In this case, society and the state take responsibility for the development and upbringing of these children. According to the questionnaire conducted by children of orphanages, the answer was that there should be orphanages. One of the main reasons for this was the goodness of the foster mothers there, the conditions and the large number of orphans and socially orphaned children. Pedagogues and psychologists studying children's problems in boarding schools found out that separation from loved ones from the early stages of life predetermines the future fate of the child.*

Keywords: *orphanage, psyche, pedagogue, pupil, emotion.*

In any country, in any society, there have been, are, and will be children without parental care. In this case, society and the state take responsibility for the development and upbringing of these children. According to the questionnaire conducted by children of orphanages, the answer was that there should be orphanages. One of the main reasons for this was the goodness of the foster mothers there, the conditions and the large number of orphans and socially orphaned children. Pedagogues and psychologists studying children's problems in boarding schools found out that separation from loved ones from the early stages of life predetermines the future fate of the child. Losing a mother and losing loved ones in general has a great impact on children's development. Because love in a person can be formed before the birth of a child. Lack of love and attention is one of the first losses for a child. A child who has lost his parents is a truly tragic world. The need to have parents is one of the strongest needs of a child. Childhood is the period of formation of the main qualities that ensure a person's mental tolerance, interest in life, and striving for a goal. These spiritual qualities are not formed randomly, they are formed in the conditions of parental love, in the conditions of the family being responsible for the child for himself and others, feeling that someone needs him. The problem of social orphanhood is a problem typical of most developed and developing countries. Unfortunately, this problem has not escaped our country either. It is difficult to list all the causes of orphanhood, because it is a multifaceted problem that scientists from different fields of science (medicine, psychology, sociology, pedagogy, etc.) are dealing with. However, we can single out three main reasons:

- parents' (usually mothers') abandonment of their minor child, mainly abandonment of a child in infancy;
- forcibly separating the child from the family after taking away parental rights from his parents;
- death of parents. The concepts of "orphan" and "social orphan" are different from each other. Orphans, one or both of their parents died before the age of 18.

Social orphans are children who have biological parents, but they are not engaged in their education for various reasons. In this case, the state and society will take care of him. The main social problems of children arise from their psychophysiological status and the objective state of the society in which they live. Children who have not seen a real, harmonious family life

are rarely able to build full family relationships. In such conditions, the importance of socially important values - family, marriage, children, parents - decreases. In recent years, crisis changes have occurred in the work of the family relations system, because most parents could not provide for their children not only socially, but also physiologically. Abandoned children are the result of the breakdown of family ties. The number of social orphans is increasing. Therefore, the state is doing everything possible to prevent the child from being transferred to a state institution for upbringing and keeping it in the family. If it is not possible to keep the child in the family, a new family is sought for him. However, when transferring a child to a new family or educational institution, everything is done to ensure that the child remains in an environment related to the ethnic group and local traditions. A system of social decisions related to child education and development is being created and strengthened in every country. We can include the following options: keeping the child in his family, returning him to his family, adoption within the country, adoption in another country, transfer to special educational institutions. If the child is not adopted or transferred to a host family, then the state institutions deal with his education and development.

Abandoned children up to 3 years of age, birth orphans are brought up in the children's home, and later they are adopted or transferred to orphanages and boarding schools. The main difference between an orphanage and a boarding school is that its pupils study in nearby schools, while pupils of a boarding school live and study in the same institution. A child growing up in a place other than his family is always an abnormal phenomenon. In the first weeks of a baby's life, upbringing without a mother in the most favorable conditions leads to a violation of its development in 90% of cases. Children raised in boarding-type institutions suffer from mental and emotional deprivation, are sensory-starved, cut off from real life. Conditions of social education, weak emotional-personal relations, imitation of family life cause social infantilism, communicative problems. In this situation, orphanages, orphanages, boarding schools are not only aimed at fulfilling educational functions, they ensure the normal socialization of the child, his full development, correct his defects, provide legal and psychological protection of educators. Some of the children can be trained according to their age, but most of the children need education suitable for children much younger than them. Usually, the children's home receives weak babies from socially undesirable families, and some of them have been treated in the hospital for a long time. Special attention should be paid to them. The specific characteristics of the children's home have their negative aspects that affect the development of the child's organism. Usually, it is difficult to ensure all-round development of the educator. However, this is the main purpose of the orphanage. An educator and a social pedagogue should reduce the impact of unpleasant factors on the child and enrich the child's life with impressions. The main task of the children's home is to ensure the full physical and mental development of children, prepare them for life in society, and facilitate their social adaptation. When organizing pedagogical work in the children's home, relying on the laws of neuropsychological development of young children, their following characteristics: speed, low level of resistance of the children's organism, close interaction of physical and mental development, children's ability to interact with adults, positive emotions, movement it is necessary to take into account the fact that there is a great need for activity, new impressions. In the children's home, great attention is paid to the health of children, especially to the protection of their nervous systems. This is the basis of movement, speech, memory, attention, thinking, visual activity, aesthetic and moral

development. If a child does not acquire the necessary skills in the first three years of his life, it will not be possible to make up for it later. Therefore, the task of the children's home is not to allow the child to fall behind in development from the first months of his life. The contingent of children raised in the orphanage is distinguished by a number of characteristics. Most children from socially unpleasant families have unpleasant social and biological analysis. If the service providers do not respond to the child's cry in time, the child's personal-emotional relationship will not be formed in time. As a result, in the first year of his life, two defects may appear in his gait. First, the child is passive, has low movement and emotional activity, which leads to the appearance of negative habits (sucking, nodding). The second is restless sleep, crying for no reason, aggressive behavior towards other children, and the result of this is the appearance of negative stereotypes in their behavior. Insufficient attention to the formation of the higher nervous system in the first year of life affects the development of this system later. In the second year of life, the child's cognitive activity decreases, the child moves aimlessly around the room, is afraid of new people or, on the contrary, seeks excessive physical contact with them. Speech development lags behind, negative habits remain. In the third year of life, the child should show the first signs of abstract awareness: the child begins to separate himself as a person, his speech can become a means of communication, and children who are brought up in other children's homes may lag behind in this regard. Nervous manifestations increase. (when the child is denied something, he may cry and throw himself on the floor), aggression towards other children, sometimes adults, increases. These are the result of objective reasons, such as the characteristics of the micro-social environment and the state of health. Taking into account the lack of interaction with adults and lack of positive emotions, it is necessary to try to replace them through educational influence on the child. In this case, the employees working in the orphanage should proceed from the normative indicators characterizing the development of higher nervous activity. Moreover, the children of the orphanage have a complicated biological and social anamnesis, and their development and health indicators are not always optimal. These aspects also reduce the activity of the central nervous system. And children of the orphanage are very easily in a state of mental stress. As for the life of the children who have just been admitted to the orphanage, first of all, it is necessary to determine where the child is coming from (from his family or the hospital) and at the same time to maintain the child's routine until now. Children's homes can be divided into preschool children's homes, preschool children's homes and children's homes for children of different ages.

The main tasks of children's homes are as follows:

- to create favorable conditions that ensure the normal development of the child, it is desirable to create conditions close to the family environment;
- maintaining children's health;
- providing medical, pedagogical and social adaptation of the child's social protection;
- protecting the rights and interests of educators;
- children's mastering of educational programs and getting sufficient education for the benefit of the individual, society, and the state;
- formation of general culture and adaptation to life of students;
- formation of self-development and self-determination needs of students.

The orphanage is the most typical institution for children under state care. Due to the presence of wide-ranging social, medical, psychological, pedagogical problems in children, there

is a need for social-pedagogical activities in the orphanage. Lack of attention from adults is a serious problem for preschool children. They have not developed enough desire to cooperate with adults. The reason that motivates children to communicate with adults is that they are attracted by adults, and children willingly accept adults' suggestions. All these communications are aimed at attracting the attention of adults. We can observe big differences between children living in families and children of orphanages, especially in terms of personal communication. The reason for this is that there is less interaction between children and adults in orphanages than in families. In an orphanage, adults pay less attention to a child, more precisely, their attention is focused on a group of children. The adults in the orphanage change, but the opposite is observed in the family. And finally, the level of emotional wealth of communication between children and adults in the orphanage is lower than that of the family.

It is typical for educators of children of primary school age that the reasons directly related to the daily activities in the orphanage and the fulfillment of the living regime there are clearly manifested. The reasons for children of this age in the family are very fruitful. This limitation of the motivational sphere depends on the living conditions of the children in the orphanage and their lack of communication with adults. This aspect is especially vividly expressed in various conflict situations: the conflict of interests of adults and children, accusations by peers, the child's lack of understanding by adults and peers, etc. Thus, scientists have determined the intellectual, behavioral and need spheres of the personality of the children of orphanages.

A child as a separate person goes through two stages in the process of forming his attitude towards himself. These stages correspond to two different periods of adolescence - the period of junior adolescence and the period of senior adolescence.

At the first stage, the child separates himself from the "children" and now seems to emphasize that he belongs to the world of adults. For this period, imitating the behavior of adults and not being able to critically evaluate his inappropriate actions, becoming too attached to a group of peers who help him to be close to adults, and similar situations is characteristic.

In the second stage, he no longer doubts that he is not a young child, and he begins to clearly understand his identity, glorify his personality, and begin to perform unique actions. By this time, his actions no longer depend on a group of peers with whom he is friends. He does not want to hear a critical opinion about his personality from anyone around him, he tries to stick to his opinion even if it is a mistake. Therefore, it is necessary to pay serious attention to the method of influencing the child during this period. Changes that occurred during adolescence, including physiological changes, not only affect his behavior and behavior, but also change his attitude to knowledge, work and its types. During this period, the child previous relationships with the environment and oneself are broken and restored, and the stage of the adolescent's entry into an independent life is formed. Taking a step into life is not a sudden event, but a long-lasting process, and its biological, psychological and social aspects have their own driving forces, their own rhythm and pace of development. Many of his demands (claims) lead to insurmountable difficulties, conflict or conflict with real reality. The practical impossibility of changing the way of life creates dreams that psychologists consider typical of this age. - if the motivations of the character are sufficiently formed, the crisis of the transitional period will pass much easier. A teenager's work considering exemplary people, appropriate imitation of high and promising goals is able to determine the subject's behavior, emotions and morals in any direction. Such

purposeful behavior is able to eliminate the conflict of motives of different directions of behavior or to level them in some sense and to provide teenagers with more internal harmony. At the same time, it should not be forgotten that adolescence cannot be covered by a single formula, as expressed by L.V. Vygotsky (1960). In order to understand its features, it is necessary to study the inner driving forces and conflicts that contribute to the mental development of this period, to distinguish the specific psychological and social achievements that reveal the nature of the entire set of signs of adolescence.

One of these main psychosocial successes is in the initial stage (12-14 years old), according to L.I. Bojovich, the stage of self-awareness that creates the opportunity for teenagers to express their thoughts and self-expression, the final stage (15-17 age) and the dream characteristic of the first stage is the self-determination of one's own destiny related to the need to solve the problem of one's future, taking into account one's real possibilities and external conditions. It is related to the need of a teenager to determine his own destiny and determine his purpose in life. Deprivation of these aspirations and needs can create a crisis seen within the framework of norms in the psychology of young people, and in some cases, psychological behavior manifestations related to the field of psychiatry. Thus, the period of adolescence that we see is characterized by the highest disparity expressed by conflicts in the level and pace of physical and mental development, which give rise to anomalous behavior in social relations, and this responsible period is a psychologist, sociologist and deserves great attention from psychiatrists and psychohygienists. If a teenager is not helped with intelligence and gentleness in "finding his identity" in such a tense period, in being aware of new interests, if the most correct ways to establish normal relations with adults are not found, then "his" Unacceptable behavior and behavioral reactions deviating from the norm of obesity may occur. Understanding the concept of "I am myself" happens in a unique way in children brought up in an orphanage. The attitude towards oneself depends on the child's intelligence and his knowledge of the environment. Now let's look at the differences in the attitude of the children living in the orphanage to themselves. Children living in the family have a very positive attitude towards themselves. Such children evaluate themselves according to the attitude of others. It should be noted that the 7-8th grade graduates of the orphanage had a very sufficient level of self-confidence. The attitude and behavior towards the surrounding people is of great importance for the child to find his own way to the future life. That's why teachers in orphanages and various children are doing positive things to teach it from a young age.

After all, this is their main task, and it is also their obligation. That is why special meetings are organized in orphanages and boarding schools. In this case, children can demand their rights in any difficult situations or in situations where they are right. Children's health problems are also added to the mental, behavioral and motivational characteristics of foster children in orphanages. In fact, there are no completely healthy children in orphanages - most children have infectious diseases. There are also disabled people among them. Cases such as taxi driving and drug addiction are typical for children of orphanages. Unfortunately, the negative effects can remain for the rest of the child's life.

According to the Czech researchers I. Langieyer and Z. Mateychek, problems related to the following areas of mental development of children of orphanages are noticeable.

1. Problems in intellectual development: in many cases there is a slowdown in mental development. In addition, they cannot even make independent decisions about the problem in

front of them. It is more convenient for them to work on the basis of a sample; In such primitive forms as interest in novelty, bright life examples, and even abnormal situations, the awareness of needs is too weakly reflected. An example can be given here of juvenile correctional colonies. However, despite their lack of motivation, their direct interest in life is clearly visible; pupils do not fully use the capabilities of a normal level of intelligence either in their studies or in their life activities. This is explained by the fact that the children are somewhat motivated and cut off from full-blooded society. This can be called "intellectual laziness".

2. Problems related to the development of the need-motivation aspect: in boarding schools, it is clearly impossible to give priority to the wishes of students directly related to daily life, routine norms, and adherence to rules of behavior. At this time, peers who study in ordinary schools think about the problems of the whole humanity, which are far from the patterns of personal experience, as well as their daily life; compared to the children of orphanages and boarding schools, the motivations of "home" children prevail, which are related to the present or the near future. The children of the orphanage have almost no perception of tomorrow or the passing of time and prefer the tradition of living with today.

3. Problems of the development of the "ME" concept: there is a misconception that children of orphanages are well socialized and have the ability to turn the situation to their own interests. But in practice it is not so. They are quite infantile, and they are more dependent on the behavior and behavior of others than children raised in higher education. Foster children, unlike "home" children, openly show their desire for independence, oppose threats and controls, and recognize the need for self-control; Self-assessment of children raised in families is more positive and has a somewhat more complex character than children raised in orphanages. A child brought up in parenting may fight against his negative traits, but at the same time, he loves himself. A child brought up in an orphanage has a one-sided attitude towards himself; Discomfort with success is often observed in foster children of orphanages.

4. Problems related to the development of gender identification: a standard of negative masculinity - feminism is formed based on poverty, a structured way of life; in many cases, children brought up in orphanages face difficulties in building their own families, find solutions to problems in parental and marital relations with difficulty; problems are observed in the formation of gender-specific behavior: in order to prevent this, educators engage in women's activities such as sewing and knitting; problems in the formation of sexual interests; the sense of responsibility occupies a small part of the imagination of the future family and motherhood.

5. Problems in relationships with adults and relatives: suspicion of people; Establishing an emotional connection with adults and relatives, even with biological brothers and sisters, is not fully formed; Unsatisfied need for affection often causes aggression; in many cases, there is a lack of respect for adults.

In order for a child to feel comfortable emotionally, physical health, communication with surrounding people, and social conditions that determine personal success are important. Of course, it is known from the experience of good children's homes and orphanages that growing up in conditions as close as possible to the family environment is an important factor that ensures successful adaptation to adult life. Thus, during the review of the scientific literature studied above, it was admitted that the personality traits, character traits, moral knowledge, mental capabilities, self-awareness and a number of socio-psychological problems of the foster children in the Mercy House, accurate sources are not enough yet. Some existing scientific works are

characterized by one-sided research, regional and regional moral-social relations do not correspond to our conditions and national values. we should not forget the indicators. As a result of the occurrence of acceleration, we can also observe cases such as character accentuation.

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